

Internship Performance of Information Technology Students at Bulacan State University – Bustos Campus

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ABSTRACT

The study aims to determine the internship performance of information technology students at Bulacan State University – Bustos. It delves into providing inputs to enhance the students' curriculum and on-the-job training experience. A descriptive quantitative research approach was employed to gather necessary information from 145 student trainees during the academic year 2022-2023. Results show that their internship performance was at an "excellent" level. It also reveals that professionalism obtained the highest mean score among the key competencies, including teamwork, communication, attendance and punctuality, productivity and resilience, initiative and proactivity, dependability and reliability, and attitude. The study recommends that Bulacan State University-Bustos continue its existing industry partnerships and expand its linkages, especially with the companies that accept information technology trainees.

Keywords: Case Internship, Information, Performance, Student

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Introduction

Internships, also known as on-the-job training (OJT), play a pivotal role in shaping the professional trajectory of students. It offers them a bridge between academic learning and practical industry experience. Students who undergo internships can develop their skills and talents, especially those not discovered and cultivated in school. They can develop a picture of the actual situations in the industry and become more responsive to the demands and advancement in their chosen field. They may develop their personality and perspectives in life. They may also become independent, especially in learning, acquiring new skills, and applying knowledge.

During the internship, students are exposed to work and make decisions at their own pace. It builds their self-reliance and establishes strong relationships between people in the organizations, including their co-trainees, staff, and superiors. It makes them reflect and realize their strengths. It helps them improve their weaknesses, which may be visible when better performance is observed. Internships are eye-openers for students to decide their future careers, learn, and establish career choices. Because of the advantages of internship, it became one of the driving forces of Higher Education Institutions (HEI) to prepare their graduates regarding the necessary skills required in the industry. The goals and objectives of the internship are the foundations to develop the relevant skills and competencies for a particular job. Both enable the translation of the training into a fruitful industry working experience (Ylagan, 2013). During the internship, students take a program that activates their experiential and active learning. They are also exposed to activities that enable learning by doing.

In those instances, the interns apply the theories and knowledge they learned from the academic institution to a natural work setting. They are also faced with job hunting as they apply for internship and practicum placement to host training establishments (THE) or agencies in their expertise. (Hawtrey, 2007). Academic courses like the Bachelor of Science in Information Technology (BSIT) have designed programs for students to comprehensively acquire knowledge and deepen

their understanding of the industry's latest information and communications technology (ICT) trends. According to the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) (2017) Memorandum Order (CMO) Number 104, Series of 2017, the internship program offers students opportunities to enrich their learnings from a college or university with relevant knowledge, practical skills, and professional attitudes. The program also aims to help students obtain proactive experience in recognized HTEs. During the program, students are exposed to work performance relevant to information technology (IT).

Furthermore, the internship is a requirement to finish a higher education curriculum. It bridges the gap between theory and practice. Internship aligns classroom education and life at work in the industry. It activates the exhibition of the precious learning experience from the four-cornered classrooms. Internship increases the significance of an academic course program and formulates the perspectives of personal and social relevance (Batool et al., 2012). It is one of the most effective techniques to improve students' competencies and abilities through practical training that exposes them to their different desired fields and, therefore, learning. It allows students to be familiarized with and educated on business operations and processes and how to deal with state-of-the-art facilities, use organizational equipment, and operate technology. The internship is also the culminating academic exercise for students from various courses and disciplines in four- or five-year academic programs. An internship conveys the students' theoretical knowledge acquired during their stay in school with relevant work experience, which may last from three months to a year. The student interns also develop their work ethics and attitudes when they apply what they have learned from books, their teachers, and other mentors in a working environment through internships. These developments are necessary for becoming efficient and influential leaders, superiors, and professionals in an organization that emphasizes multidisciplinary and cross-cultural endeavors (Laguador, 2013).

Bulacan State University-Bustos (BulSU-Bustos) is one HEI that offers BSIT undergraduate programs and employs its students to work as HTEs for their internships. The institution requires 486 to

500 hours of training program. The BSIT students are examined physically and psycho-emotionally; they are ensured academic eligibility and permission from their legal guardians before being deployed to highly sought-after IT HTEs. BSIT students are also equipped with internship orientation and seminars to ensure that they understand their roles and responsibilities as interns. To ensure their status and condition, they are visited in the HTEs by the faculty members handling the internship. It also aims to confirm if the BSIT program at BulSU-Bustos contributes to the growing IT workforce and human capital. This scenario influenced the researcher to conduct the present study. It delved into determining the internship performance of the BSIT students to describe their responsiveness during training in terms of teamwork, communication, attendance and punctuality, productivity and resilience, initiative and proactivity, judgment and decision-making, dependability and reliability, attitude, and professionalism. Moreover, to further contribute to the University's commitment to its stakeholders, BulSU-Bustos must be aware of the feedback from the HTEs during their students' internship since the quality of performance during the training program dramatically relies on the training provided and the supervision of the HIE and the HTE (Narayanan et al., 2010). Also, the study's results may provide information necessary further to improve the implementation of the BSIT internship program.

Methodology

This study is anchored with the Experiential Learning Theory. According to Simons et al. (2012), this theory posits that knowledge is gained through experience. It emphasizes the importance of concrete experiences, reflective observation, abstract conceptualization, and active experimentation, making it highly relevant for analyzing internship performance. It employed a descriptive quantitative research approach to accurately and systematically describe the target population (McCombes, 2022). The data were gathered from the performance of the BSIT students who were enrolled in the internship program of BulSU-Bustos during the academic year 2022-2023. The evaluation of 145 student trainees based on the Intern's Performance Appraisal Form of BulSU was purposely used. The appraisal form includes nine

(9) aspects: teamwork, communication, attendance and punctuality, productivity and resilience, initiative and proactivity, judgment and decision-making, dependability and reliability, attitude, and professionalism. The researcher used a five-point Likert scale to assess the degree of performance of the BSIT interns for every statement in the appraisal form. The scale used has a gap of 0.8 with values from one to five, limits and interpretation of 1.00 to 1.80 for poor, 1.81 to 2.60 for fair, 2.61 to 3.40 for good, 3.41 to 4.20 for very good, and 4.21 to 5.00 for excellent.

Before the actual conduct of the study, the researcher first defined the research objectives and the sources from which the data was collected. Then, the researcher prepared a communication letter addressed to the university ethics committee requesting permission to conduct the study. Once permitted, the researcher informed and asked for the consent of the BSIT interns to use their performance evaluation. To minimize bias, the researcher ensured accurate, complete, and relevant data collection. The collected data underwent cleaning coding and verification. It was managed with accuracy and integrity. The data was tabulated, analyzed, and computed using weighted mean. After the analysis, the results were discussed and interpreted to report the findings. Most importantly, the researcher ensured ethical considerations, such as informed consent, confidentiality, and anonymity, throughout the data-gathering procedure.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 shows the BSIT interns' positive results regarding teamwork. It can be observed that each statement has an associated mean score, ranging from 4.51 to 4.68, interpreted as excellent. The statement treated all team members respectfully and courteously and gained the highest excellent mean score of 4.68. It is followed by the statement that willingly works with team members to continuously improve team collaboration, with a mean of 4.63, which is described as excellent. The statement consistently works with others to accomplish goals and tasks, with a mean of 4.60, which is described as excellent.

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Table 1. Evaluation of the BSIT Interns Regarding Teamwork

Statement	Mean	Interpretation
1. The intern reliably works with other interns and staff to accomplish the set goals and tasks.	4.60	Excellent
2. The intern respectfully and courteously treats all the company's team members and other staff.	4.68	Excellent
3. The intern shows willingness when participating in different activities and accomplishing the assigned tasks.	4.56	Excellent
4. The intern enthusiastically works with team members to continuously improve team collaboration.	4.63	Excellent
5. The intern considers feedback positively and reflects on team members' views when accomplishing the assigned tasks.	4.51	Excellent
Average Mean	4.60	Excellent

Table 2 presents the scores of the BSIT interns on key communication criteria. An average score of 4.40 is interpreted as excellent. The criteria were also excellent, with 4.65 as the highest for the statement of listening conscientiously to supervisors and co-workers and 4.27 as the lowest for reliably providing feedback as required, both internally and

externally. The highest and lowest means scores are the statements that comprehend written and oral information and consistently deliver accurate information, with excellent mean scores of 4.35 and 4.32, respectively. The excellent mean scores indicate that interns excelled at attentively listening to supervisors and colleagues. This is a crucial foundation for effective communication, ensuring understanding instructions, tasks, and project goals (Lucas, 2022). They have a good understanding of written and oral information necessary for processing and critical thinking (Zoller et al., 2022).

Table 2. Evaluation of the BSIT Interns Regarding Communication

Statement	Mean	Interpretation
1. The intern listens conscientiously to the supervisor and co-workers.	4.65	Excellent
2. The intern comprehends written and oral information.	4.35	Excellent
3. The intern consistently delivers accurate information	4.32	Excellent
4. The intern consistently provides internal and external feedback	4.27	Excellent
Average Mean	4.40	Excellent

Table 3 shows the evaluation scores of the BSIT interns regarding attendance and punctuality. The highest excellent mean score obtained is 4.60 for the statement informing the supervisor promptly if absent or late. It is followed by the statement that maintains good attendance and participation with a mean of 4.56, described as excellent. The lowest mean score of 4.43 is obtained by the statement that it is consistently punctual, still described as excellent. All of the indicators obtained excellent ratings with an average mean of 4.53. These scores mean that interns generally arrived at work on time. This situation demonstrates respect for colleagues, supervisors, and the work schedule (Galbraith & Mondal, 2020). They consistently attend and actively participate in work activities, contributing to project continuity and fostering a positive work environment (Akpa, et al., 2021). The scores of the BSIT interns signify that they can promptly

communicate any absences or lateness to their supervisor. This character demonstrates proactive communication and respect for the supervisor's time (Zoller et al., 2022).

Table 3. Evaluation of the BSIT Interns regarding Attendance and Punctuality

Statement	Mean	Interpretation
1. The intern is consistently punctual.	4.43	Excellent
2. The intern maintains good attendance and participation.	4.56	Excellent
3. The intern informs the supervisor promptly if absent or late.	4.60	Excellent
Average Mean	4.53	Excellent

The information in Table 4 offers insights into the interns' performance regarding productivity and resilience. Two statements obtained the highest mean of 4.45, described as excellent. These two statements consistently deliver quality results and inform the supervisor of task challenges or barriers. The highest obtained mean is 4.40, which is excellent because the statement meets deadlines and manages time well. However, the lowest scores of 4.34 and 4.31 were earned by the statements that work and handle problems and challenges professionally to accomplish the given tasks and effectively manage time, respectively.

Nevertheless, both are still interpreted as excellent. BSIT interns' excellent average mean score is 4.40. These scores suggest that the interns have consistent quality work, can meet deadlines and have time management skills, can solve problems in stressful situations efficiently, and can communicate challenges to supervisors. In IT, meeting deadlines and managing time effectively are crucial for completing projects on schedule (Zoller et al., 2022). Resilience allows professionals to adapt to changing priorities and work effectively under pressure (Zoller et al., 2022). Moreover, strong problem-solving skills enable IT professionals to troubleshoot technical issues and find efficient solutions (Driskell et al., 2018).

Table 4. Evaluation of the BSIT Interns regarding Productivity and Resilience

Statement	Mean	Interpretation
1. The intern consistently delivers quality results.	4.45	Excellent
2. The intern meets deadlines and manages time well.	4.40	Excellent
3. The intern works and handles problems and challenges professionally to accomplish the given tasks.	4.34	Excellent
4. The intern has effective and efficient time management skills.	4.31	Excellent
5. The intern notifies the supervisor of any challenges that emerge in tasks.	4.45	Excellent
Average Mean	4.40	Excellent

Table 5 provides valuable insights into the interns' level of initiative and proactivity during the internship. The table outlines excellent scores from criteria to average mean. The highest mean score of 4.53 is earned by the statement that engages in continuous learning with an excellent interpretation. It is followed by the statement that seeks additional support, when necessary, with a mean of 4.52, described as excellent. The statements complete tasks independently and accurately, complete assignments with minimal supervision, and recognize and take appropriate action to effectively address problems; they also obtained excellent mean scores of 4.43, 4.41, and 4.39, respectively.

However, one statement obtained a very good interpretation. It is the statement to contribute new ideas and seek ways to improve the organization or workplace with a mean of 4.14. Still, the BSIT interns' performance means they can work independently, seek support when needed, be problem-solvers, exhibit continuous learning, suggest new ideas, and contribute to workplace improvement. As BSIT interns, being proactive makes them more professional in anticipating issues and developing solutions before they become significant problems. They can take the initiative to

suggest new ideas and improvements, which can be highly valuable. BSIT interns can also adapt to changing technologies and work independently, which are crucial skills for success in the IT field (Zoller et al., 2022).

Table 5. Evaluation of the BSIT Interns regarding Initiative and Proactivity

Statement	Mean	Interpretation
1. The intern completes the assignments with minimal supervision.	4.41	Excellent
2. The intern independently and accurately completes tasks.	4.43	Excellent
3. The intern seeks additional support when needed.	4.52	Excellent
4. The intern distinguishes and takes appropriate measures to solve problems effectively.	4.39	Excellent
5. The intern is involved in continuous and vital learning.	4.53	Excellent
6. The intern contributes new ideas and seeks ways to develop the organization or workplace.	4.14	Very Good
Average Mean	4.40	Excellent

Table 6 shows the scores of the BSIT interns regarding judgment/decision-making. The statements analyze problems effectively and demonstrate good judgment in handling routine problems. Both got excellent mean ratings of 4.23 and 4.22, respectively. Meanwhile, the statement that can showcase the skills and talents to produce relevant and creative solutions to problems only scores 4.13, which is very good. The average mean is 4.19, which is described as very good. BSIT interns, individually or in groups, can be highly effective in analyzing and coping with problems and providing judgment in daily challenges.

Table 6. Evaluation of the BSIT Interns regarding Judgement and Decision-Making

Statement	Mean	Interpretation
1. The intern effectively analyzes and addresses problems .	4.23	Excellent
2. The intern can showcase the skills and talents to produce relevant and creative solutions to problems.	4.13	Very Good
3. The intern demonstrates sound judgment in managing routine problems.	4.22	Excellent
Average Mean	4.19	Very Good

The data in Table 7 shows positive results regarding the interns' dependability and reliability. It has an average mean of 4.53, which is interpreted as excellent. Each statement has an associated excellent mean score, ranging from 4.43 to 4.60, suggesting a positive evaluation of dependability and reliability. The statement earns the highest mean rating of 4.60 and adapts effectively to changes in the work environment. It has an interpretation of excellent. The next highest excellent mean rating is 4.53 for the statement to follow through and meet required deadlines.

Table 7. Evaluation of the BSIT Interns regarding Dependability and Reliability

Statement	Mean	Interpretation
1. The intern can follow through and meet deadlines.	4.53	Excellent
2. The intern shows accountability for every action.	4.46	Excellent
3. The intern effectively adapts to changes in the workplace and environment.	4.60	Excellent
4. The intern consistently displays an outstanding level of high performance.	4.43	Excellent
Average Mean	4.53	Excellent

In the third spot is the statement that is personally accountable for his/her actions, with a mean of 4.46, described as excellent. The lowest mean score of 4.43 is for the statement with a consistently high performance level, which is still interpreted as excellent. These results mean that BSIT interns' reliable performances ensure that project timelines and milestones are met, which is crucial for successful project completion (Zoller et al., 2022). They established dependability for building trust and maintaining positive client relationships (Zoller et al., 2022). The BSIT interns were also able to form reliable team members who contribute to a positive and productive work environment (Driskell et al., 2018).

Table 8. Evaluation of the BSIT Interns regarding Attitude

Statement	Mean	Interpretation
1. The intern willingly offers assistance when needed.	4.61	Excellent
2. The intern positively contributes to the values and morale of the organization.	4.50	Excellent
3. The intern sensitively shows affection and considers the feelings of others.	4.45	Excellent
4. The intern constructively and positively accepts criticism.	4.51	Excellent
5. The intern shows pride and confidence when performing tasks.	4.33	Excellent
Average Mean	4.48	Excellent

Table 8 outlines the scores obtained by the BSIT interns regarding attitude. It can be gleaned that all the indicators have excellent scores. The statement earns the highest mean score of 4.61 that he/she willingly offers assistance when needed. It has an interpretation of excellent. It is followed by the statement that it accepts constructive criticism positively, with a mean score of 4.51, described as excellent. The statement positively contributes to the organization's morale and has a mean of 4.50, which is described as excellent.

Meanwhile, the lowest mean scores of 4.45 and 4.33 were obtained by the statements that they accept constructive criticism positively and show pride in performing tasks, respectively. Still, both are interpreted as excellent. Overall, the provided mean scores and the average mean score suggest that the BSIT interns possess a positive attitude characterized by a willingness to help, contribution to morale, sensitivity to others, acceptance of feedback, and pride in work (Podsakoff et al., 2000). Specifically, their willingness to help fosters teamwork and collaboration within the organization. They explicitly contribute positively to morale, enhancing employee engagement and satisfaction (Grawitch et al., 2015). The BSIT interns' sensitivity and consideration contribute to a supportive and inclusive work environment (Eisenberger et al., 2019). They accept constructive criticism positively, which promotes personal and professional growth (Kluger & DeNisi, 1996). Moreover, the BSIT interns took pride in tasks that enhanced motivation and job satisfaction (Ashforth & Humphrey, 1995).

Table 9. Evaluation of the BSIT Interns Regarding Professionalism

Statement	Mean	Interpretation
1. The intern respects those in authority.	4.84	Excellent
2. They responsibly use tools, carefully use equipment, and sensibly operate machines.	4.63	Excellent
3. The intern follows all the organizations' policies, rules, and procedures, especially when issues arise, and conflicts emerge.	4.53	Excellent
4. The intern sticks with the policy manual and appropriate procedures, issues arise, and conflicts emerge.	4.50	Excellent
5. The intern shows an appropriate physical appearance to the work environment and placement rules.	4.61	Excellent
Average Mean	4.62	Excellent

Table 9 shows the excellent evaluation of BSIT interns in terms of professionalism. Respect for authority obtained the highest mean score of 4.84, which is described as excellent. It is followed by the statement that responsibly uses tools, equipment, and machines, with a mean score of 4.63 and an excellent interpretation. On the third rank is the statement that physical appearance is appropriate to the work environment and placement rules, with a mean rating of 4.61, which is described as excellent. The statement that follows all the organizations' policies, rules, and procedures, especially when issues arise and conflicts emerge, has a mean of 4.53, interpreted as excellent.

Meanwhile, as issues and conflicts arise, the statement sticks with policies and procedures. They got the lowest mean score of 4.53, which is still excellent. The average mean score for professionalism is 4.62, which is interpreted as excellent. These scores indicate that BSIT interns have a strong respect for authority figures. Respect is necessary for the workplace to foster a positive work culture and organizational harmony (Bilginoglu et al., 2019). The interns demonstrated competence and caution in handling tools and equipment. They are responsible for using resources that promote safety and efficiency in the workplace (Osborne & Hammoud, 2017). The BSIT interns ensured compliance with policies and procedures during challenging situations. Their consistency in applying policies and procedures ensures reliability and fairness in resolving workplace challenges (Omisore & Abiodun, 2014) and transparency and integrity in decision-making (Greenwood et al., 2011). The excellent scores also emphasize that BSIT interns' personality suits a professional work environment. Physically, their grooming and attire contributed to a respectable image and organizational reputation (Jung & Seock, 2016). The overall performance of the BSIT interns regarding professionalism was exceptional. This is a crucial quality for success in any professional setting, and the interns have demonstrated a strong foundation in this area.

Table 10. Overall Performance of the BSIT Interns

Statement	Mean	Interpretation
1. Teamwork	4.60	Excellent
2. Communication	4.40	Excellent
3. Attendance and Punctuality	4.53	Excellent
4. Productivity and Resilience	4.40	Excellent
5. Initiative and Proactivity	4.40	Excellent
6. Judgment and Decision Making	4.19	Very Good
7. Dependability and Reliability	4.53	Excellent
8. Attitude	4.48	Excellent
9. Professionalism	4.62	Excellent
Average Mean	4.46	Excellent

A summary of the overall performance of the BSIT interns is shown in Table 10. An average mean of 4.46 means that BSIT has an excellent internship performance. The criterion of professionalism obtains the highest mean score of 4.62. This result suggests that the interns demonstrated professionalism through respect, responsibility, policy adherence, and appropriate behavior. It is followed by teamwork with a mean of 4.60, interpreted as excellent. The BSIT interns excel in collaborative efforts, demonstrating the ability to work effectively with others towards common goals. Attendance, punctuality, and dependability/reliability obtained an excellent mean score of 4.53. This shows that the interns exhibited good attendance and punctuality, showing reliability in fulfilling work commitments. They also have a high level of dependability and reliability, essential for consistent performance and trustworthiness.

The criterion attitude garnered a mean score of 4.48. This result implies that the BSIT interns displayed a positive attitude towards work, colleagues, and tasks, contributing to a conducive work environment. Communication, productivity res, resilience, and initiative all obtained a mean score of 4.40, interpreted as excellent. BSIT interns showed effectiveness in conveying ideas and information. They have a commendable level of productivity and resilience, indicating

the ability to maintain performance and bounce back from setbacks. They also bestowed initiative and proactivity in acting and seeking solutions. Meanwhile, the lowest mean score of 4.19 is obtained by judgment/decision-making, which is still interpreted as excellent.

Conclusion

The study's findings show that the overall internship performance of the BSIT interns is excellent. Their performance in the key competencies, including teamwork, communication, attendance and punctuality, productivity and resilience, initiative and proactivity, dependability and reliability, attitude, and professionalism are also excellent. Meanwhile, the BSIT intern's judgment/decision-making is very good. Although the internship performance of the BSIT are very good and excellent, room for improvement is still open to achieve much better results, especially in the implementation of the internship program. The BSIT program should emphasize training students on how to contribute creative ideas and pave the way for them to become a part of the improvement of an organization. Simulations and practical performances that will enable students to think divergently may be applied across subjects in the curriculum. To improve their judgment and decision-making, they may be given more situations for their analysis to become more comprehensive and in-depth. They should be exposed to relevant scenarios that feature stress and pressure in the workplace to enhance their creativity. There should also be routine activities of solving problems from simple to complex for every class in core and general education subjects to help them handle various challenges and obstacles.

The study is based on the feedback of the supervisors from the HTE. With the excellent internship performance of the BSIT students, the university should continue to expand its partnerships and linkages to the highly sought-after HTEs in the field of IT. The BSIT program must continue the conduct of orientation seminars and the practice of providing receipts and evaluation of all documents submitted by the student interns. These actions ensure the completeness, timeliness, and veracity of documents. The program and the

faculty handling the internship should ensure continuous agreement and understanding through a memorandum to protect the reputation and ensure the responsibilities of all the stakeholders involved. The BSIT program must also continue testing the physical and psychological dimensions of the interns and ensure their academic integrity and legal guardians' permission. The highly qualified faculty handling the internship should visit as frequently as possible, according to the prepared plan of HTE, to ensure close monitoring of the student interns. They must also ensure that BSIT interns may accomplish the required number of training hours in preparation for graduation and early application to companies or HTE.

Moreover, improving the program would provide benefits and impacts to the university's stakeholders and may contribute to achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Improving the BSIT internship program may enhance employability skills aligned with SDG 4: Quality Education, which aims to promote skills development for better job opportunities and lifelong learning. It is parallel to fostering industry-academe collaboration which is supported by SDG 17: Partnership for the Goals. This SDG emphasizes the importance of collaboration between educational institutions and HTEs. Furthermore, it connects to promoting sustainable practices in education. It stresses SDG 8: Decent Work and Economic and Growth, which advocates for sustainable economic growth and job creation through effective internships. With these, BSIT students can gain essential skills, learn sustainable practices, and access better internships. Teachers can adjust curricula, build industry connections, and incorporate economic growth and development into their teaching. Lastly, administrators will create new partnership frameworks and promote sustainable policies regarding the BSIT internship program.

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